

IMPORTANCE OF FAIRY TALES IN MORAL EDUCATION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: *A fairy tale is considered one of the main genres of folk oral poetic creation and is based on fiction and fiction [Uzb.t.i.lug', vol. 5, 52]. In fairy tales, which are among the types of works of art, created in different genres, the events are not based on facts. Most of the events described in fairy tales are far from reality.*

Keywords: *Socialization, spiritual and moral qualities, negative social effects, formation of immunity, protection from psychological stress, preparation for school education, creative development, socio-pedagogical activity.*

Аннотация: *Тарбияланувчиларни ижтимоийлаштиришида уларда маънавий-ахлоқий сифатларни шакллантириши ва физиологик, психологик ва ижтимоий оғишларнинг олдини олиши ҳамда қайта тиклаш, салбий ижтимоий таъсирларга нисбатан иммунитетни ҳосил қилиши, уларни психологик зўриқишдан ҳимоялаш, мактаб таълимига тайёрлаш, шунингдек, ижодий ривожлантириши каби йўналишлар ижтимоий-педагогик фаолиятни ташкил этиши мақсадга мувофиқ саналади*

Калит сузлар: *Ижтимоийлаштириши, маънавий-ахлоқий сифатлар, салбий ижтимоий таъсирлар, иммунитетни ҳосил қилиши, психологик зўриқишдан ҳимоялаш, мактаб таълимига тайёрлаш, ижодий ривожлантириши, ижтимоий-педагогик фаолият.*

A fairy tale is considered one of the main genres of folk oral poetic creation and is based on fiction and fiction [Uzb.t.i.lug', vol. 5, 52]. In fairy tales, which are among the types of works of art, created in different genres, the events are not based on facts. Most of the events described in fairy tales are far from reality. Nevertheless.

fairy tales have a great educational effect on enriching the thinking of preschool age (as well as primary education) students, expanding the world of fantasy, developing their fantasy, and increasing the wealth of speech. Fairy tales, first of all, develop imagination in children. Tales with artistic and didactic potential reflect folklore, historical and educational plots.

The word "fairy tale" is recorded in written sources created before the 16th century. Lexically, the Russian word "skazka" is formed on the basis of the term "kazat". This term means: list, order, clear statement. The modern concept of "skazka" in the Russian language was fully formed in the 19th century. Before that, the terms "basn" ("parable"), and "koshchuna" ("wisdom, wisdom") were widely used until the 11th century.

The word "tale" ("skazka") means "to learn about something", "to understand what it is" and to understand "why" what is said.

In the family, fairy tales were used by children to consciously and involuntarily understand social existence, to understand social rules and life goals, and to teach them to communicate properly with others. Fairy tales have served to convey to generations a large amount of information about their life experiences. Sources provide information about the existence of several types of fairy tales. Including:

1. Folk tales (they contain traditional folklore plots and are enriched with folk songs, lapars, games).
2. Tales about animals, plants, inanimate nature and objects (various animals, plants, birds, inanimate nature and objects are chosen as the heroes of the tale, and the main content is revealed based on their characteristics; the characteristic aspect of such tales is that animals, plants, inanimate nature or objects they speak, they move, in a word, they show human aspects in themselves).
3. Magic fairy tales (the main theme of such fairy tales is magic, supernatural power, they are focused on "searching for something", "liberating someone", "enchancing someone (or something)"; for such fairy tales, "flying carpet", characters such as "self-walking boots", "invisibility cap", "hot khumcha", "a giant who fulfills all

wishes (a demon, a gnome, a spirit or a goldfish, etc.) are chosen; at the end of the tale, the main characters achieve their

4. Tales that tell historical events that have become legends (historical events are developed on the basis of exaggerated qualities, heroes are described as unequal in strength, intelligence, understanding and behavior; their uniqueness is based on historical evidence).
5. Household fairy tales (based on social relations and rules for their organization, children are given information about them).goals and, of course, the winner will be).
6. Tales that represent extraordinarily sharp mental capacity, insight and conscious behavior.
7. Anecdotes (fairy tales based on a small number of characters, which are not very complicated in terms of the plot; the characters help to find a solution to a certain problem according to their sharp mental capacity, thinking, ability to think, and the ability to be present).
8. The category of fairy tales (in such fairy tales, the development of events is enriched with the help of certain images or characters; certain situations are told as independent tales; for example, household life, social relations, through the images of Efendi in Uzbek folk tales, Aldarkosa in Kyrgyz folk tales, and Omirboy Lakki in Kazakh folk tales) it tells about the attitude to certain activities and kindness between people).

Fairy tales differ from legends in their own way. The differences between them are:

- 1) a specific time and place are represented in a legend and they serve to reveal mysterious information, and for fairy tales, the geographical location is not important;
- 2) historicity is a characteristic aspect of legends, and historicity is not so important in fairy tales;
- 3) the legend was formed on the basis of some reliable information, and the main condition of the tale is to be rich in interesting plots;
- 4) there are aspects that are unique to fairy tales and legends, which are: oral narration, collectiveness, and unknown authorship.

Tales usually begin with the words "If there is, if there is no", "in some country" ("in some kingdom"). In many cases, the storyteller can also be a participant in the events of the story in the form of "I was there too", "I also saw this event with my own eyes". For most fairy tales, certain characters are chosen as heroes. For example, for Uzbek folk tales - Kachal Polvan, Puchukoy, Karbobo, Karqiz, for Russian folk tales - Ivanushka-durochok, Vasiliy Bogatyr, Ded Moroz, Snegurochka, for Arab folk tales - Shahrizoda, Sinbad, English folk tales - Gnomes, Santa Claus, Blackbird (Belosnejka) and others are the main characters. For almost all folk tales, the negative image of the old woman Yalmogiz is chosen, and her image is depicted as scary and evil. His house is also depicted differently from ordinary houses, ie, this house with two chicken legs moves in a circular motion. Another unique feature of this character is that he can fly using his broomstick.

In various national tales, the phrase "If it weren't for your greetings, I would win one yamlab two" is used to teach children the simplest rules of etiquette. The positive heroes of fairy tales appear as a beautiful princess, a brave prince, a hard-working craftsman, a farmer who is a master of his work, and wise old men.

Preschool age children's behavior is based on emotional experiences, emotionality is reflected in their activity, mobility, reactions to the events happening around them. Most children at this age "express their success or failure by displaying appropriate emotional reactions in their activities. Most children of this age simply emphasize the result achieved; some perceive successes and failures through positive and negative emotions. In this age group, self-esteem is especially noticeable after achievements in activities. The child is not only happy with the achievements, but with a figurative and expressive display of his successes, a unique sense of pride is manifested. However, even such a simple self-esteem is very little noticeable at this age.

It is only after children reach the age of 3.5 years that a public reaction to successes and failures can be observed, reflecting self-evaluation. According to one of the psychological studies, three-year-old children have simple ideas about their

personal capabilities. ... And four-year-old children have the opportunity to more accurately assess their capabilities".

The formation of a sense of self-esteem in children of preschool age allows them to approach their behavior from a moral point of view. Now they categorize actions by themselves or others as positive or negative. They try to evaluate social subjects, including their actions as "bad" or "good", "possible" or "impossible", "correct" or "not correct". As a result of the inculcation of national values into the content of education in family and pre-school educational institutions, the concepts of "merit" and "sin" are also used as evaluation criteria for children's behavior and attitudes towards the activities of others. In most cases, the actions of peers are judged by saying, "It's meritorious to do this" or "It's a sin not to do it."

At preschool age, children try to evaluate their own behavior and others based on certain moral standards. They develop some moral ideas, as well as moral self-control.

In the socialization of students, the formation of spiritual and moral qualities and the prevention and restoration of physiological, psychological and social deviations, the formation of immunity to negative social influences, the protection of them from psychological stress, the preparation for school education, as well as the organization of creative social-pedagogical activities considered appropriate.

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